

Paper and thin layer electrophoresis of metal ions and anions – a review

S. D. Sharma

Analytical Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001, India

Manuscript received 17 December 1999, revised 3 October 2001, accepted 28 December 2001

In this review an attempt has been made to cover the salient features of paper electrophoresis (PE) and thin layer electrophoresis (TLE) as applied to the analysis of metal ions and anions present singly or as multicomponent mixtures. It covers the general practices of PE and TLE, effect of various factors and the applications which have been subdivided into different categories, viz. PE of different group metal ions and radioisotopes on plain and impregnated papers, rare earths, anions, and TLE of metal ions and anions. The tables include important reviews published earlier, the technical data on the inorganic species studied, and the separations carried out under the conditions of potential gradient and time. A need is strongly felt for the wider applications of these simple and inexpensive techniques in geological, pharmaceutical and environmental analysis.

Introduction

In recent years, Capillary electrophoresis has become a popular technique for the separation and analysis of inorganic mixtures consisting of ions or charged particles. The separations are achieved by the differences in migration rates for sample components in an electric field applied to a capillary tube filled with an electrolyte. The presence of an electric field causes the movement of sample ions by electrophoretic migration and bulk flow of the electrolyte solution by electroosmosis. The various modes of capillary electrophoresis (CE) include capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE) in which ions are separated according to their relative mobility (approximately equivalent to their size-to-charge ratio) in free solution. In capillary gel electrophoresis (CGE) ions are separated by their electrophoretic mobility through a porous gel network. In general, ion mobility through a gel network decreases as the ion size increases. CGE, therefore, is ideally suited to the separation of oligomers which have a constant charge-to-mass ratio. Electrophoretic capillary chromatography (ECC) is a variant of CZE in which a pseudo-stationary phase is added to the electrolyte solution and allows a separation to be achieved based on the distribution of the sample between the bulk of electrolyte and the pseudostationary phase. The pseudostationary phase is usually a surfactant such as cyclodextrins or a polymeric ion exchanger. A unique feature of ECC is that it can separate neutral molecules as well as ions. Another variation of the CZE method is capillary isoelectric focussing (CIF), which is suitable for the separation of amphoteric compounds, such as proteins. The separation capillary is filled with sample and a mixture of ampholytes used to create a pH gradient. When an electric field is applied the ampholytes migrate to their respective isoelectric points and form a relatively stable pH gradient. The sample components migrate electropho-

retically through this gradient until they reach a pH at which their net charge is zero. The separated zones are detected by displacing the electrolyte solution passed a suitable detector by applying pressure to one end of the capillary. In capillary isotachopheresis (CITP) the sample solution is sandwiched between a leading and a terminating electrolyte. The leading electrolyte contains ions with a mobility higher than that of any ion in the sample and conversely the terminating electrolyte contains ions with a mobility lower than that of any of the sample ions. When an electric field is applied, the leading electrolyte will attempt to *pull away* from the sample ions. This results in a gap where the conductivity is dropping and the electric field is rising. The increased field will *pull* the analyte ions along until their velocity reaches that of the leading electrolyte and all the sample ions are migrating as single bands arranged in order of their relative mobility and with an identical velocity. Detection in isotachopheresis is sometimes achieved by UV absorption, but more commonly electrical methods are used. The various modes of capillary electrophoresis (CE) represent a new approach to electrophoretic separations rather than the application of a new separation principle. They offer faster separations, higher efficiency, reliable quantitative detection and ease of automation.

A good number of reviews on CE have recently appeared in literature. However, the technique requires sophisticated instruments and other automation facilities due to which it is financially out of reach of many laboratories in developing countries like India and hence the need for inexpensive techniques arise which suit to the requirements of small laboratories having limited instrumentation facilities. As a result, paper and thin layer electrophoresis may enjoy popularity as the inexpensive, rapid detection, preconcentration, separation and limited quantification techniques for a wide

variety of applications in inorganic sample analysis. Although a number of reviews on paper electrophoresis (PE) and thin layer electrophoresis (TLE) have appeared since 1952 (Table 1), it is worthwhile to review extensively, since the very beginning, the PE and TLE of inorganic species such as metal ions and anions.

Table 1. List of important reviews on PE and TLE of metal ions and anions

Sl. no.	Title	Reference
1.	Chromatography and analogous differential migration methods	Strain <i>et al.</i> (1952)
2.	Chromatography and analogous differential migration methods	Strain <i>et al.</i> (1954)
3.	Chromatography analysis by differential migration	Strain (1958)
4.	Paper electrophoresis	Sugano (1960)
5.	Electrochromatography of metal ions	Bailey <i>et al.</i> (1961)
6.	Thin layer electrophoresis and electrochromatography	Hashimoto <i>et al.</i> (1963)
7.	Electrophoresis	Strickland (1964)
8.	Electrophoresis	Strickland (1966)
9.	Significance of radio isotopes for paper electrophoretic and immunoelectrophoretic studies	Kallee (1967)
10.	Chromatography and electrophoresis of inorganic ions in fused salts	Alberti <i>et al.</i> (1968)
11.	Zone electrophoresis on paper in inorganic analysis	Ryabchikov <i>et al.</i> (1968)
12.	Some recent results in inorganic paper chromatography and electrophoresis	Lederer (1968)
13.	Zone electrophoresis on paper in inorganic analysis	Korchennaya <i>et al.</i> (1971)
14.	Zone electrophoresis on paper, thin layer and pevikon block	Smith (1979)

Paper electrophoresis

In 1937, the first communication by Konig¹ on the use of paper electrophoresis (PE) appeared in portugese. The use of UV-light was suggested for locating separated substances which was much used in chromatography. Two years later Konig and Van Klobusitzky² used it for the separation of a yellow pigment from a snake venom, its first use for protein mixtures. However, this work attracted little attention. The initial development in PE were confined up to the separation of organic compounds. Berraz³ in 1943, sepa-

rated inorganic ions by paper chromatography which paved the way for paper electrophoresis of inorganic species that was largely taken up after 1950. The linearity of electrophoretic movement of ions with respect to time was first established by McDonald *et al.*⁴ making some modifications in the apparatus previously used by them⁵. Electrical contact with the buffer solutions was made by agar-KCl salt-bridges. The dry paper strips were placed in the Bakelite frame and wetted by immersing the frame in the buffer solution. The excess liquid was allowed to run off and the frame was then placed in position in the chamber. Kraus and Smith⁶ studied electromigration of inorganic substances on filter paper strips. For the control of temperature, the moist paper protected by glass may be cooled with water by contact with a metal block. However, continuous electrophoresis principle was introduced by Grassman⁷ and Svensson⁸ who designed an apparatus for continuous electrophoretic separation in flowing liquids, a method having no parallel in contemporary chromatography. Durum^{9,10}, a pioneer in the field, gave a microelectrophoretic and microionophoretic technique for inorganic ions inside filter paper and described an apparatus and technique based on continuous electrophoresis. Strain *et al.*¹¹⁻¹⁶ performed continuous and discontinuous electrophoresis and separated many ions including rare earths. They summarized the differential migration methods and gave the requirements for the analysis. The electrochromatographic sequences^{11,17} in moist porous media due to differential electrical migration have been given and continuous electrophoretic separation of inorganic ions in milligram to decigram regions and in trace amounts alongwith the influence of experimental conditions was reported. Also the effects of nature, concentration and pH of the electrolyte alongwith the field strength and the type of paper used were investigated. Some other studies on the factors influencing migration of ions were reported and during the process the electroosmotic flow^{18,19} of liquid was attributed to a driving force within the paper.

By using PE, the separation of phosphorus^{20,21} and sulfur acids^{22,23}, and the microseparation of platinum metals were carried out and high voltage electrophoretic separation of inorganic ions with special attention to the platinum metals was given²⁴⁻²⁶. Majumdar and Singh²⁷⁻³⁰ studied electromigration of various ions in different electrolytes. Later, the electrophoretic technique was improved by coupling it with X-ray fluorescence, UV illumination, autoradiography, radioactive tracers, photoelectric screening, radiometric detection, neutron activation and G-M-detection etc. Analysis of mixtures of cations was carried out in NH₄OH media³¹. Some other studies on the separation of

Pt metals were reported³²⁻³⁴. Earlier, Lederer^{35,36} studied inorganic metal ions and anions and later reported 'High performance' paper electrophoresis of metal ions. PE was also applied for the determination of the charge-sign of zirconium ions and the behavior of perchlorate, hexacyanoiron(II) and hexacyanoiron(III) ions was studied. The separation of rare earths alongwith that of La^{III} and Ac^{III} was carried out by Lederer and many others³⁷⁻⁵⁵. The influence of type and pH of electrolyte, distance from electrodes, size and form of the paper were examined⁵⁶. The concentration of ligand ion used in electromigration of rare earth metals was also determined. The optimum conditions⁵⁷ for the separation of ions were studied by measuring the relative rates of their migration and some inorganic ions were separated in fused salts on glass fibre paper.

Bailey and Yaffe⁵⁸ reviewed the electrochromatography of metal ions on plain papers. Few years later, Ryabchikov *et al.*⁵⁹ reviewed the zone electrophoresis on paper in inorganic analysis. However, the separation potential of the technique on papers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers increased as the selectivity of the ion exchange material for certain ions also played an important role in their electrophoretic migration leading to separations which were not usually possible under the influence of electric field only. Alberti *et al.*⁶⁰ was probably the first to use papers impregnated with synthetic inorganic ion exchangers for the electrochromatographic separation of metal ions. Later, Ying-Bo-Hai⁶¹ made attempts in this direction. A number of studies using papers impregnated with synthetic inorganic ion exchangers have since been reported.

Evans and Strain⁶² showed improved separation of alkali metal ions from alkaline earth ones by the addition of complexing agents to the background electrolyte. The separation of alkali metal ions by migration in solutions that convert all the polyvalent cations and monovalent silver and thallium into anionic species have been achieved. In PE complexing agents of various types have been used particularly for the separation of transition metal ions, and the complexation effect of tartaric, citric and oxalic acids on migration of metal ions using stannic arsenate and titanium tungstate papers have been extensively studied.

MoO₄²⁻ and ReO₄⁻ were separated in HCl electrolyte at 13 V/cm⁶³ and electrical mobility of phosphate ions were determined⁶⁴. Cr₂O₇²⁻ decomposed during electrophoretic studies in lactic acid media⁶⁵. Various anions were studied in HCl and KCl media⁶⁶ as well as in metal salt solutions^{67,68}. Effect of pH on electrophoretic behavior of anions was also studied⁶⁹ and separation effects were interpreted in terms of degree of ion-pair formation⁷⁰. An

empirical relationship between ionic mobilities and migration values of univalent anions has been established⁷¹.

Thin layer electrophoresis

Thin layer electrophoresis (TLE) was introduced by Consden, Gordon and Martin⁷² in 1946, who separated a mixture of amino acids and peptides on silica-gel thin layer. In 1961, TLE on silica-gel as stationary phase was performed by Honegger⁷³ for amino acids and amines. TLE and electrochromatography have been reviewed by Hashimoto and Mori⁷⁴. The early literature was reviewed by Hannig and Pascher⁷⁵ and Sargent⁷⁶ which led to the development of a range of equipment. The earliest attempt of the ionophoresis of inorganic ions using a film of agar gel on a slide was carried out by Pfrunder *et al.*⁷⁷, followed by Dobici and Grassini⁷⁸ who were the first to separate iodate and periodate on gypsum thin layers. Moghissi⁷⁹ separated inorganic cations and anions using radionuclides and Bergamini *et al.*⁸⁰ separated and identified alkali metal ions by radial thin layer electrophoresis. The separation of lanthanides by thin layer high voltage electrophoresis was reported by Bachmann and Gorisch⁸¹. The separation and quantitative determination of radioactive iridium compounds on silica gel and cellulose layers was reported by Van Ooij and Houtman⁸². Makrova and Stepanov⁸³ separated Ce, Pm and Eu in complexone III solution. Spacers were used for electrophoretic separation of radioactive sodium and potassium ions on cellulose thin layers⁸⁴.

However, TLE could not keep pace with the developments in paper electrophoresis, which was so extremely simple to carryout. Only recently it was taken up again after Stahl had shown, how to prepare the thin layers of adsorbents. However, the rise of planar gel electrophoresis and the ease of performing conventional TLC seem to have resulted in the lack of interest in the technique.

In 1974, Pretorius *et al.*⁸⁵ described a technique which they termed 'High speed thin layer chromatography' by applying 25 kV across a prewetted silanized silica gel plate. Unfortunately, lack of details and experimental methodology could not make it worthwhile. However, this clearly demonstrated that electrophoresis can be used to achieve rapid separations. In later years, this technique was not explored further thereby causing an end to this noble attempt. A literature survey reveals that planar electrophoresis was reviewed for the work carried out upto 1979. After that a few papers were published using this technique for the separation of metal ions due to the emergence of 'capillary electrophoresis' which offers faster separations, higher efficiency, reliable quantitative detection and ease of automation. Af-

ter a long gap, there was a resurgence of interest in the field when Sharma and Misra⁸⁶ performed thin layer ionophoresis of *d*-block metal ions and also carried out low voltage thin layer ionophoresis of DMSO complexes of metal ions⁸⁷. Pukl *et al.*⁸⁸ also made some significant contribution in this field. A recent communication⁸⁹ has admirably highlighted that use of electrophoresis remains a neglected area in modern planar chromatography and emphasized the need to revisit these techniques.

A survey of literature reveals that not much have been done in the TLE of inorganic species and as far as we are aware the majority of work has been performed on cations

as only three papers appeared on the study of anions⁷⁸⁻⁹⁰. However, very few attempts have been made using PE and TLE for analyzing the natural mixtures or inorganic substances, alloys and the inorganic species present in biological, pharmaceutical and environmental samples. Some of the technical data on PE and TLE of metal ions and anions are given in Tables 2 and 3. In spite of a number of review articles published in the past four decades, the one covering PE and TLE of metal ions and anions has not appeared. This article includes the work carried out upto June 2001. The publications in the field upto 2000 are given in Fig. 1.

Much care has been taken in the compilation of litera-

Table 2. Applications of paper electrophoresis of metal ions and anions*

Inorganic species	Remarks	Ref.
(a) Metal ions and radio isotopes :		
Ca, Sr, Ba, Mg	These ions show an indential behavior, their separation is not possible under the conditions employed; migration of ions was studied as a function of pH at 20°	117
Fe, Mn, Cu, Ni	Cu and Ni separated from cupro-nickel Indian coin and determined spectrophotometrically. The main constituents of pyrolusite were separated at 2.2 V/cm in 15 min	118
Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Tl ⁺ , Th ⁴⁺ , UO ₂ ²⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	Ternary, quaternary and polynary metal ion mixtures were separated at 5 V/cm in 2 h	119
Metal ions	Detection of cation on acid pherograms using ferric thiocyanate and fluorescein or bromophenol blue	177
Ag ⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Sb ³⁺ , Sn ⁴⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Na ⁺ , K ⁺	Binary, ternary or quaternary separations of metal ions	120
Twenty one cations	Separation and indentification of cations at pH 3 and 10 V/cm	170
Mn ²⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , V ⁵⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , Cr ³⁺	Five cations were separated with 0.75 N lactic acid at 900 V in 25 and 30 min	94
Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Al ³⁺	Cations separated in acid medium at 400 V	95
Pt ⁴⁺ , Rh ³⁺ , Os ⁴⁺ , Pd ²⁺ , Au ³⁺ , Ru ³⁺ , Ir ⁴⁺	Separation of microgram quantity of ternary and quaternary mixtures of ions into distinct zones at 100 and 200 V in 3 h	24
Au ³⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Pd ²⁺ , Ir ⁴⁺ , Rh ³⁺ , Ru ³⁺ , Os ⁴⁺	Four ions in microgram quantity separated in distinct zones at 150 V in 5 h	26
Pt ⁴⁺ , Pd ²⁺ , Rh ³⁺ , Ir ⁴⁺	Pt metals quantitatively separated in microgram amounts	171
Be ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , Zr ⁴⁺ , Th ⁴⁺ , UO ₂ ²⁺	Binary, ternary and few quaternary separations obtained at 150 V in 5 h	27
A number of univalent, bivalent and trivalent metal ions	Analysis of mixtures of cations carried out	31
Copper and tin group metals	Complete separation of all the copper group ions from a mixture using HCl, NaCl and KCl as electrolyte at 150 V in 5 h; only binary separation of tin group ions achieved	28
Silver group metals (Ag ⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ and Tl ⁺)	The mixture of ions separated into distinct zones using NaCl, KCl or KCN as the electrolyte at 150 V in 3 h; migration sequence is Hg-Ag-Pb-Tl	29
Zinc group metals (Zn ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺)	A number of ternary separations achieved; a quaternary separation with ions having the migration sequence Ni-Zn-Co-Mn is possible in presence of KCN solution at pH 6.0; all separations achieved at 150 V in 3 h	30
Cu, Pb, Cd, Bi, Hg, Co, Ni, Pd, Fe	Various separations achieved, e.g. Cu-Fe, Pd-Hg at 10 V/cm, Rh ³⁺ from Ir ⁴⁺ . Pd ²⁺ from Au ³⁺ and As from Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn; copper group ions separated in 15 min at 10-12 V/cm	156

Table 2 (contd.)

Ca ²⁺	Various factors such as dimensions of paper, electrolytic solution, its concentration, volume and concentration of the mixture to be resolved, presence of salts and of mineral acids in this mixture, electrical potential, electrode reactions and distance of migration influenced the separation studied; radioactive calcium quantitatively separated by counting the activity of the separated ion	126
Ca-45, Sr-90, Y-90, Ba-140, La-140, Pb-210, Bi-210, Po-210, Ra-226	Effect of concentration and sorption upon migration of cations studied at 3, 5 or 7 V/cm for 20–24 h; effect of concentration upon the separation of radium from its principal radioactive daughters and from barium determined	123
Ag ⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ and many radioactive ions	The electrochromatographic sequences of various cations determined at 160–400 V for 2–4 h providing basis for the detection and identification of various cations and new analytical separations based on one-way migration and continuous electrochromatography	127
Metal ions	Separation of metal ions can be made by applying complex forming agents in a narrow band on the supporting medium	160
Metal ions	A number of radioactive and inactive ions separated	108
Am-241, Cm-244, Ce-144, Eu-152 + 154, Gd-153, Tb-160, Tm-170	Am and Eu separated at 9 kV, 6 mA in 1, 2, 3 and 4 (pH = 3.2); separation of Am and Cm at 3 kV, 30 mA in 4 h (pH = 1.6)	137
Metal ions	Rapid method for the qualitative analysis of mixtures of metal ions at 30 V/cm and current density of 1–1.5 mA/cm ²	176
Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	Effect of pH variations in separation of Cu ²⁺ and Zn ²⁺ determined with 0.1–0.5 N potassium sodium tartarate as effluent at 170 V	101
Al ³⁺	For the electrophoretic migration of the ion, the optimal conditions of voltage, pH of electrolyte and migration time determined	111
Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺	A mixture of Cu ²⁺ and Cd ²⁺ can be separated at 200 V, 6 mA in 36 h at 20°	100
Ru, Rh, Pd, Os, Ir, Pt	Separations at 250 V in 3.5 h	112
Sr-90, Y-90, Ba-137, Ce-137, Tl-208, Pb-212, Bi-212, Po-210, Bi-210, Pb-210	The separation of Y-90 from Sr-90, Ba-137 from Ce-137 and Tl-208 from Pb-212 and Bi-212 in radioactive mixtures achieved at 150–300 V at a few mA for 1–5 min	121
Pm-147	Pm-147 having impurities of Eu-154, Eu-155 and Ce-144 purified by paper electrophoresis	208
Metal ions	Metal ions in sulfate solutions have a displacement inversely proportional to their valencies	203
Metal ions	0.04–0.08 mg Ni separated and determined; spot treated with rubeanic acid and the intensity measured	206
Metal ions	Bi, Cd, Cu, Hg, As, Cu, Sb, Sn, and Cu separated from Au, Pt and Pd	190
Fe, Cr, Ni, Mn, Co, Zn, Cu	Fe, Cr, Ni, Mn, Co, Zn and Cu can be separated on ion exchange paper and the sensitivity increased 1.5–3 times in comparison to that on conventional paper	128
Mn ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , A ⁸⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺	Binary and ternary metal ion separations achieved in 2% and 5% NaNO ₂ solution at 5 V/cm	194
Cu ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Mobilities of ions were determined after, applying corrections for electroosmosis and added migration path length	188
Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu group metal ions	Separation of copper group metals in 0.5 N HCl electrolyte occurred in the same order as for a paper chromatogram with butanol containing HCl; ionophoretic separation of Co ²⁺ and Ni ²⁺ as thiocyanate complex was analogous to that obtained in paper chromatography with butanol containing HCl and also KCNS	189
U ⁶⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺	Effect of pH on electrophoretic mobility studied, separation of U ⁶⁺ from Ce ³⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ and Cu ²⁺ at ≈ 1 kV and 10 mA in 20 min	195
U ⁴⁺ , U ⁶⁺	Separation of micro amounts of U ⁴⁺ and U ⁶⁺ achieved in 7–10 min at 2000–3000 V	183
Pt metals	The mobility of chloro complexes of these metals decreased in the order Ir, Os or Pt, Rh, Pd, Ru	32

Table 2 (contd.)

Radio elements and their disintegration products	Separations at 80 V/cm at 15°; relative speeds of migration of Na ⁺ , Cs ⁺ and Fr ⁺ in the order : Fr ⁺ (= Cs ⁺) > Na ⁺	196
Pt metals	The effect of pH, concentration and nature of acid used investigated; migration is in the order : Ir, Pt, Os, Rh, Pd, Ru	25
Pt metals	Separation of Pt metals most effective in α -hydroxyisobutyric acid	33
Pt metals	Separation of Pt metals	34
UO ₂ ²⁺ , Co, Cu, Ni, Zn, Cs, MoO ₄ ²⁻ , WO ₄ ²⁻	Separation of UO ₂ ²⁺ from Co, Cu, Ni, Zn, Cs, MoO ₄ ²⁻ and WO ₄ ²⁻ at 600 V and 1.5 mA	131
RaD (Pb-210, RaE (Bi-210), RaF (Po-210)	0.05–1.0 N is the optimum HCl concentration for separation of elements	186
Fe, Cu, Zn, Pb	Detection of heavy metal contamination in pharmaceuticals at 300 V in 3 h	181
Cs-137 Ce-144	Separation of radionuclides	185
Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Qualitative separation of Fe ²⁺ from Fe ³⁺	124
Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Separation and determination of Fe ²⁺ and Fe ³⁺ at 22 V/cm in 15 min; relative errors were < ± 4.3% for determining μ g amount of Fe ²⁺ and Fe ³⁺	132
Cu ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Small amounts of Cu ²⁺ in Pb(OAc) ₂ ·3H ₂ O, Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ ·18H ₂ O and FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O or Fe ²⁺ in CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O or Fe ³⁺ in Pb(OAc) ₂ and Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ separated from main component and determined; in the determination of 0.2–1% impurity, the relative deviations ranged 3–10%	197
Rh, Pd, Pt, Au, Se, Te	Separation of fine elements from a mixture at 110–130 V in 1–2 h	172
ortho-, pyro-, tri- and trimetaphosphates (condensed phosphates)	Most successful separation of ortho-, pyro, tri- and trimetaphosphates in 0.05 N HNO ₃	178
UO ₂ ²⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺	UO ₂ ²⁺ separated from Ce ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ and Cu ²⁺ at 1000 V, 20 mA in 30 min	198
La ³⁺ , UO ₂ ²⁺	Separation of La ³⁺ from UO ₂ ²⁺ at 550 V and 5 mA in 30 min; electrohoretic mobility vs pH graphs gave S-shaped curves	133
Mo, V, Se, U, Th, Ta, Nb, Ti	Mixture of Nb-Ta, Mo-Ta-Ti, Th-U, Mo-U and Mo-V-U separated at 500 V; effects of electrolyte concentration, voltage, current and time investigated	173
Metal ions	The influence of type and pH of the electrolyte, distance of the starting point from the electrodes, size and form of the paper examined	56
Cr ³⁺ , CrO ₄ ²⁻	Separation of Cr ³⁺ and CrO ₄ ²⁻ at 1–1.5 KV in 5–10 min; peak areas found to be rectilinearly proportional to concentration	107
Sixtyfour metal ions	Electromigration behavior studied	134
Fourteen metal ions	Separations of Sr-Ca, Sr-Ba, Ba-Ca-Zn-Cd, Fe ³⁺ -Co-Ni-Cr ⁶⁺ , Mn ²⁺ -Fe ³⁺ , Fe-Co-Ni-U ⁶⁺ , Mn ²⁺ -Ni-Co-Th-Cr ⁶⁺ , Th-U ⁶⁺ -Pb, U ⁶⁺ -Eu ³⁺	182
Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , Cs ⁺ , Tl ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺	Mobilities of alkali metal ions in LiClO ₄ -KClO ₄ eutectic at 300° increase as their crystalline radius decreases; for alkaline earth metal ions dissolved in the same solvent an opposite behavior observed; mobility of a cation dissolved in various fused salts having the same anions but different cations or vice versa reported and discussed	157
Thirteen metal ions	Use of chelate compounds to better the separations examined	192
Fe ²⁺ and Fe ³⁺	Good separations obtained at 12 V/cm in 30 min with μ mole of each species	124
Re ³⁺ , Re ⁴⁺ , Re ⁷⁺	Re ³⁺ , Re ⁴⁺ and Re ⁷⁺ can be separated at 19 V/cm, 20–30 mA in 15 min	136
Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , Cs ⁺	The mobilities of ions were measured and useful separations obtained in nitromethane, 0.2 M in ammonium formate and 0.4 M in trichloroacetic acid at 15 V/cm in 3 h	125
Cu, Zn, Ag, Cd, Pb, Hg, Bi, As, Sb	Quantitative separation of metal ions	179
Alkali metal ions, Ag ⁺ , Tl ⁺	Separation of alkali metal ions from each other, from Ag ⁺ , Tl ⁺ and Ag ⁺ and from various multivalent ions	207

Twenty six metal ions	Mobility of metal ions compared to their R_f values on Amberlite resin paper	106
$^{51}\text{Cr}^{3+}$ and $^{51}\text{CrO}_4^{2-}$	Separation of two oxidation states of chromium using radiochromium(^{51}Cr) as tracer	135
Metal ions	Metal ions separated in a heated oven at 2–5 V/cm	158
Alkaline earth metal ions and bivalent heavy metal ions	Levelling effect of ligand buffers on chelate stabilities examined and stability constants estimated	53
Thirty seven metal ions	Binary and ternary separations, selectivity of metal ions; prediction of elution sequence of metal ions on the basis of migration	149
Alkali metal ions	The mobility is in the order of the effective ion size due to hydration	204
Twenty metal ions	Binary and ternary separations achieved at 4.7 V/cm	187
Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions	Separation of alkali metal ions from the alkaline earth metal ions varied greatly with the composition and pH of the background electrolyte solution	62
Cu, Cd, Pb, Bi, Co, Ni	Quaternary separations such as Cu-Cd-Pb-Bi, Co-Cd-Pb-Bi, Ni-Cu-Pb-Cd, Co-Cu-Pb-Cd, Ni-Cd-Pb-Bi at 150 V	129
Ag, Tl	Separation of Ag and Tl ions from each other and from mixtures of various polyvalent cations	180
Al^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Fe^{3+}	Separation of Al^{3+} (10 V/cm, 1 h at pH 11), separation of Hg^{2+} (7.9 V/cm, 40 min at pH 1.7), separation of Fe^{3+} (10 V/cm, 2 h at pH 2.2) from various cations	199
Radioactive Zr-95	Charge-sign of Zr ions determined at 300 V	200
Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+}	Cu and Zn metal ions separated from other elements in brass at 270 V, and 6m A; mean error, $\pm 2\%$	99
Al^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{4+} , Tl^+ , As^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Au^{3+} , U^{6+} , V^{5+}	Cations were separated from mixtures	184
Ag, Pb, Hg, Bi, Cd, Cu, Fe Mn, Ni, Co	The migration of cations is influenced by the concentration and type of cations present, concentration of carrier electrolyte, temperature and sorptive capacity of the paper	130
Cu, Co, Ni, Pb, Mn, Fe, Al, Mg, Zn	Separation of ions as complexes	193
(b) Metal ions on impregnated papers :		
K, Rb and Cs	Separations achieved at 6.3–12.5 V/cm in 50–100 min	138
Thirty two metal ions	Binary, ternary and quaternary separations obtained; quantitative separation of U and Pt from several metal ions and synthetic mixtures	139
Twenty nine metal ions	Binary, ternary and quaternary separations involving 22 metal ions; microgram separation (25–100 μg) of Pt^{4+} from Pt group metals and other metal ions	140
Fifteen transition metal ions	Binary and ternary separations of metal ions at 200 V in 3 h; Ag^+ (2–10 μg) and Au^{3+} (2–10 μg) separated quantitatively from Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pt^{4+} and Pd^{2+} (5 μg each) in the synthetic mixtures	141
Metal ions	Binary and ternary separations obtained, e.g. Sm^{3+} - Tm^{3+} , Eu^{3+} - Dy^{3+} , Bi^{3+} from Fe^{2+} or Cu^{2+} or UO_2^{2+} , Hg^{2+} - Ag^+ - V^{4+} , Cs^+ - Rb^+ , Ba^{2+} - Sr^{2+} , Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} , Mo^{6+} - W^{4+} , Dy^{3+} , Er^{3+} etc. at 80–200 V in 5–6 h	115
Forty six metal ions	Binary separations of Hg^{2+} from 45 metal ions, Au^{3+} from 41 metal ions and Pd^{2+} from 43 metal ions; Mg^{2+} and Pd^{2+} quantitatively separated from binary mixtures as well as synthetic mixtures at 40–200 V in 4–6 h	114
Fifty two metal ions	Binary separations achieved; mechanism of migration explained in terms of precipitation, ion-exchange and adsorption	110
Forty nine metal ions	Various binary and ternary separations achieved at 50–100 V in 3–8 h	109
Metal ions	Effect of DMSO, pH and charge of metal ions on ionic mobility studied, binary and ternary separations obtained and papers selective for Hg and Zn at 100 V in 3–8 h	142
Forty six metal ions	Fe^{2+} separated from binary and ternary mixtures containing other metal ions at 100–200 V in 4 h	113
Metal ions	Ba, Sr and Tl separated from various metal ions and some binary separations achieved, e.g. Bi-Tl, Hg-Tl, Se-Mo, Te-Mo, UO_2 -Mo, Cr-Mo, In-La	143

Table 2 (contd.)

Twentyone metal ions	Binary and ternary separations at 250 V in 2 h	144
Thirtytwo metal ions	Pd ²⁺ (2–10 μg) quantitatively separated from binary and synthetic mixtures	145
Fifty metal ions	Binary and ternary separations on plain and impregnated papers, e.g. Zr ⁴⁺ separated from Th ⁴⁺ , In ³⁺ , Y ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺ , Pr ³⁺ , Nd ³⁺ and Sm ³⁺ at 100 V in 8 h	146
Metal ions	La, Pr and Sm separated on impregnated papers of 4.7 V/cm; Ni ²⁺ and Cd ²⁺ separated either on Whatman No. 3 or Amberlite SA-2 papers	60
Fortyeight metal ions	Separations of alkali metal ions; electromigration explained in terms of complexation, precipitation and ion exchange	148
Fortyeight metal ions	Binary and ternary separations achieved, e.g. Fe-Cr, Sr-Ba, Pt-Ru-Cu and Au-Pd-Cu at 40–100 V in 3–8 h	147
Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , V ⁴⁺ , V ⁵⁺ , Pt ²⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , Sn ⁴⁺	Separation of Fe ²⁺ -Fe ³⁺ , V ⁴⁺ -V ⁵⁺ , Pt ²⁺ -Pt ⁴⁺ and Sn ²⁺ -Sn ⁴⁺ achieved	151
Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , U ⁶⁺ , V ⁴⁺ , V ⁵⁺ , Pt ²⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , Sn ⁴⁺	Separation of U-Fe, Ni-Cu, Fe ²⁺ -Fe ³⁺ , V ⁴⁺ -V ⁵⁺ , Pt ²⁺ -Pt ⁴⁺ and Sn ²⁺ -Sn ⁴⁺ achieved	152
Pd ²⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺	Separation of Pd ²⁺ and Pt ⁴⁺ from Fe ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ and Cu ²⁺ ; papers impregnated with trioctyl amine resulted in tailing of the analyte zones	150
Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺	Effect of ion exchange on ionic mobilities observed; mobilities markedly reduced by ion exchange resins particularly on sulfonic papers	153
La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Y	Quantitative separation of La, Pr plus Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd and Y at 100–200 V/cm	105
Twentyseven metal ions	Binary, ternary and quaternary separations	154
Nineteen metal ions	Separations of metal ions; mobilities of ions depend on the ion exchange properties of thorium phosphate and the nature of the complexes formed with the electrolyte	155
(c) Rare earth metal ions :		
Rare earth elements	Separation of rare earths on the basis of pH variation. Continuous paper electromigration of La-Ce and La-Nd, separation factors > 10	38
Rare earths	Rare earths electrophorised at 300 V for 3.5 h The electromigration sequence similar to that on ion exchange columns	37
Rare earths	Various binary and ternary separations obtained, e.g. Nd-Pm, Ce-Pr, Ba-La and Sr-Y	39
Lanthanides	Separation of Ce ⁴⁺ from Y ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Pr ³⁺ , Nd ³⁺ , Sm ³⁺ , Gd ³⁺ and Dy ³⁺ at 3 or 6.1 V/cm and of La ³⁺ from Y ³⁺ , Dy ³⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺ from La ³⁺ , Pr ³⁺ , Nd ³⁺ , Sm ³⁺ and Sm ³⁺ from Y ³⁺ , Dy ³⁺ at 2.1 V/cm in 3 h	40
Rare earths	Separation of La-Ac and other mixtures at 300 V	41
Rare earths	Series of 11 rare earth element mixtures composed of three or more components separated; focussing spectrum agrees well with the series of stability of the rare earth element complexes	42
La and rare earths (Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd)	Rare earth metal ions separated at 100–200 V/cm; error of spectrophotometric determination, ± 20%	43
Rare earths	Rare earth metals separated from monozite sand at 6.5–10 V/cm	44
Sc, Y, lanthanides, Th, Zr, U	Elongated spots observed with weak electrolyte solution; good separations of heavy and light lanthanides obtained with concentrated sodium or ammonium sulfate solutions	45
Pa and other metals	Purification of Pa by separating Zr, Ti, Nb and Ta from it	46
Sm, Nd, Y, Pr, La, Ce, Sc, Ac	Separation of lanthanides and homologs of lanthanum obtained at 300 V in 45 min	47
Y ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Pr ³⁺ , Nd ³⁺	Separation of Y ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Pr ³⁺ and Nd ³⁺ investigated	48
Ce ³⁺	Behavior of the ion at nearly 10 ⁻¹¹ and 10 ⁻⁵ M concentration studied	49
Rare earth elements	Migration behavior of individual rare earth elements studied alongwith their separation; respective rate of migration related to their atomic number; rare earths in 0.05 M citric acid migrate as anionic complexes	50
Th, rare earths, U	Separation from monozite and allanite at 1400 V in 2.5 h	51
La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Eu, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, Lu	Separation of rare earth present in chondritic meteorites	52

Table 2 (contd.)

Rare earth metal ions	Levelling effect of ligand buffers on chelate stabilities examined and stability constants estimated	53
Nd, Sm, Eu	Separation of Nd and Sm at 300 V in 25 h	54
La, Ce, Pr	Separation of La from Ce and Ce from Pr; optimum concentration of ligand ion determined	55
(d) Anions :		
MoO_4^{2-}	MoO_4^{2-} and ReO_4^- , separated at 13 V/cm in ≤ 15 min in 0.30 N HCl solution; trace amounts of Re detected in presence of large amounts of Mo	63
I^- , CNS^- , $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, CrO_4^{2-} , NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, BrO_3^- , $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$	The order of movement of anions at 3.65 V/cm for 50 min was not related to their ionic mobilities but closely follows the order of adsorption on Al_2O_3 impregnated paper strips	156
H_2PO_4^- , $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-}	Electrical mobility of phosphate ions determined at 3 V/cm in 3 h; electroosmotic flow and mobility vary with pH	64
$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, SCN^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-}	Electrophoretic studies of anions for 20 min; $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ion decomposed during migration	65
PO_4^{3-}	Factors influencing the separation of phosphate ion studied; radioactive phosphate ion quantitatively separated	126
IO_3^- , IO_4^-	Separation of IO_3^- and IO_4^- at 400 V in 1.5 and 2 h	78
Anions	Qualitative separation of anions; ammonium carbonate gave better results than citric acid	176
PO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-} , SeO_3^{2-} , TeO_3^{2-} , $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$	PO_4^{3-} and SO_4^{2-} ions can be separated at 150 V, 30 mA in 2 h, SeO_3^{2-} and TeO_3^{2-} ions separated at 150 V, 30 mA in 2 h, separation of ferricyanide and ferrocyanide possible in 50 min using N KCl	66
Thirtyone anions	Ternary separations ClO_3^- - BrO_3^- - IO_3^- and BrO_3^- - IO_3^- - IO_4^- alongwith separation of BO_3^{3-} from numerous metal ions at 150 V in 1 h	67
Twelve oxoacidanions of phosphorous and ortho-, pyro- and triphosphate anions	Separation of nine oxoacid anions; effect of pH on electrophoretic behavior studied	69
Twentyone anions	Inorganic anions studied using various metal salt solutions as electrolytes; metal ions has a strong effect on the movement of anions both by ion-pair and complex formation	122
ClO_3^- , BrO_3^- and IO_3^-	The electrophoretic movement of ions studied at 1000 V for 30 min; separation effects were interpreted as differences in the degree of ion-pair formation	70
ClO_4^- , ClO_3^- , BrO_4^- , BrO_3^- , IO_4^-	Separation of perbromate from all halates and other perhalates except ClO_3^- in thorium nitrate and zirconyl chloride at 1000 V in 30 min	68
I^- , IO_3^- , TeO_3^{2-} , TeO_4^{2-}	Rapid separation of anions	104
Ten univalent anions	An empirical relationship between ionic mobilities as determined by conductivity and migration values as determined by electrophoresis given; adsorption on paper is negligible except in case of IO_4^-	71

*Stabilization medium, background electrolyte and technique employed for the above applications are mentioned in the text.

Table 3. Thin layer electrophoresis of metal ions and anions

Inorganic species	Remarks	Ref.
Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , IO_3^- , IO_4^-	Separation of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{2+} at 120 V in 10–12 min	77
Metal ions and anions (SCN^- , SeO_3^{2-} , TeO_3^{2-} , I^- , IO_3^- , Cl^- , ClO_3^- , Br^- , BrO_3^- , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-})	Quantitative separation of periodate and iodate in mg at 300–400 V in 1.5–2 h	78
Alkali metal ions (Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs)	Separations carried out at 13 V/cm or 45 V/cm using radionuclides. High voltage ionophoresis carried out for 2–5 min	79
	Separation and identification of alkali metal ions at 450–500 V, 40–45 mA dc in 30–40 min. mobility sequence is $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K} > \text{Rb} > \text{Cs}$	80

Lanthanides (Ce, Pm, Eu)	Separation of Ce, Pm and Eu in 1.1M α -HIBA (pH = 2.4) at 60 V/cm in 2 h	81
Mono-, di- and triphosphates Ce, Pm, Eu	Qualitative separation of polycondensed phosphates at 400 V Trace amounts of metal can be separated, cellulose powder more effective compared to silica gel	167 83
Re ⁷⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , V ⁵⁺ , W ⁶⁺	ReO ₄ ⁻ , MoO ₄ ²⁻ , VO ₃ ⁻ and WO ₄ ²⁻ separated at 400 V, 1-3 mA in 30 min; microgram amounts of MoO ₄ ²⁻ determined	168
d-Block metal ions	Binary and ternary separations obtained, e.g. Pd ²⁺ -Rh ³⁺ , Th ⁴⁺ -Zr ⁴⁺ , Hg ₂ ²⁺ -Hg ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ , Pd ²⁺ and Pt ⁴⁺ separated from various metal ions	86
Cu ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻ , SCN ⁻ , Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻ , Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻	Qualitative and quantitative separations of ions at 5 V/cm, high resolving power of poly(vinyl alcohol) carrier and high selectivity of separation of ions tested	169
Metal ions and anions	The effect of pK of metal oxalate and metal citrate complexes on the migration of metal ions discussed ReO ₄ ⁻ (10 μ g) was quantitatively separated from other anions and their mixtures	90
Thirtyfour metal ions Ba-140, La-140	Metallic ions separated at 300 V/6.5 cm in 5 min: electrophoresis of Ba-140 and La-140 carried out for 5, 6 and 10 min and about 90% separation of La-140 obtained in 10 min	163
Twenty inorganic ions	Separation of inorganic anions at 300 V/6.5 cm in 5 min; others it occurs at acid pH; very similar ions separated	164
Common inorganic ions	Complex formation for some ions only at higher pH and for others it occurs at acid pH; very similar ions separated	165
Metal ions	Electrophoretic ion focussing of inorganic ions and the relation between the amount focussing area and concentration of the electrolytes described	166

TLL = Thin layer ionophoresis

ture. However, any omissions are purely inadvertant and are highly regretted.

Methodology

Martin and Syngé used the term ionophoresis to define

Fig. 1. Number of publications on PE and TLE of metal ions and anions (1937-2000).

'process concerned with the movement in an electric field of relatively small ions, electrophoresis for the movement of large molecules and particles and electro dialysis for the removal of small ions from larger molecules and particles'. In PE and TLE, a paper or thin layer is uniformly moistened with a suitable electrolyte, solute and the substance mixture to be separated is applied on the moist layer or paper as a spot or band and an electric field applied. The substances migrate at different rates and in a direction depending upon their charges. The electrophoretic migration of an ion depends upon its charge, size, shape, hydration, tendency to dissociate, amphoteric behavior etc. in addition to the properties of the electrolyte such as nature, concentration and the pH of the electrolyte solution, ionic strength, dielectric constant, chemical properties, temperature, viscosity, presence of non-polar molecules and the type of paper along with the intensity of the applied field⁹¹⁻⁹³. The other factors affecting the mobility of ion with in the stabilization medium are : (a) adsorption, (b) diffusion, (c) zone flows, (d) zeta potential and electroosmosis and (e) suction effects.

(A) Techniques :

Various electrophoretic techniques are used for the separation of inorganic ions.

One-dimensional electrophoresis : The substance mix-

ture is applied on the plate or paper with a micropipette as a spot or band to the start line which is chosen according to the expected direction of migration of the given species. The electric field is applied in a direction right angle to the start line and the start points marked with a hard pencil^{94,95}.

Two-dimensional electrophoresis : Electrical migration in one direction in one solvent followed by electrical migration in a transverse direction in the same solvent have been called two-dimensional electrophoresis. In principle, however, this use is not different from continued electromigration in one direction, although it has the possibility of revealing small differences among the trailing regions of zones that are not revealed by extended oneway migration. In this technique, the substance mixture is applied at 4–5 cm from the plate or paper edges and a volatile electrolyte is used for first dimensional run which is completely removed before the second run.

Continuous and discontinuous electrophoresis : In continuous electrophoresis (Refs. 7, 8, 10, 25, 38, 41, 44, 96–101), a narrow stream of the mixture is continuously introduced when both electrolyte and electric current flow through the porous media. Under such a set-up, the various components follow separate paths through the medium and electrolyte. The porous media may be powdered glass, special filter paper between glass sheets or sheets of filter paper suspended in a closed atmosphere saturated with solvent vapor to prevent evaporation. The narrow zone of mixtures may be introduced through a special cell, through a wick of filter paper or through a hypodermic needle from a syringe compressed by a screw driven by a synchronous motor. In discontinuous electrophoresis^{39,96} a spot or small zone of the mixture is added to the moist porous medium. The porous media may be powdered glass, various filter aids, paper or ion-exchangers. Downward displacement of the solutes is caused by chromatography or flow of solvent. Horizontal displacement is caused by electrolysis. The separation of the mixture results in the formation of a series of zones or spots in the porous medium.

High voltage electrophoresis : High voltage electrophoresis (Refs. 25, 43, 52, 79, 81, 83, 104–108) is the method employed above 20 V/cm potential gradient. In the process, the main problem is the dissipation of heat due to passage of current. The problem was solved by keeping the paper strip or plate in intimate contact with a cooling plate which is cooled by circulating water or a refrigerant.

(B) Methods :

The paper electrophoretic methods are as follows : (i) *closed strip method (evaporation prevented)* having (a)

solid support like glass and plastic, (b) non-polar liquid (as immiscible liquid seal); (ii) *semi-closed strip method (evaporation permitted)* having solid support-one side; (iii) *open strip method (evaporation permitted)* – minimum area of (a) horizontal type^{109–112} and (b) hanging strip type^{113–115}

In the usual set of equipment for TLE, the thin layer plates rest on a water-cooled metal plate. The electrical contact is made between electrode compartments filled with electrolyte and the layer by using a strip of filter paper moistened with the electrolyte used.

(C) Stabilization medium :

Paper : Various types of papers generally in the form of strips are used. As an exception, filter paper of fan like shape is also employed¹¹⁶. (a) *Unmodified papers* : Papers can be washed with distilled water or dil. HCl or EDTA or 1M HNO₃ to remove trace impurities. The examples are : Whatman 3 mm paper^{78,100,136,137}, Whatman No. 226–30,¹²⁹ Whatman No. 120¹³⁰, Whatman No. 4^{131–133}, Whatman No. 41, 31, 3,¹³⁴ Whatman No. 540¹³⁵, Whatman No. 3 and Amberlite SA-2⁶⁰, Whatman No. 31^{51,54}, Whatman No. 1^{40,66,68,70,117–122}. Eaton-Dikeman grade No. 301^{39,123–127}, monocarboxycellulose paper (ion exchange grade)¹²⁸. (b) *Modified papers* : To minimize the adsorption and electro-osmosis, surface is modified by acetylation, esterification with diazomethane or 2-aminoethylsulfuric acid etc. (c) *Impregnated papers* : Different types of impregnated papers are used, e.g. ammonium molybdophosphate¹³⁸, zirconium(IV) tungstate¹³⁹, zirconium(IV) phosphate antimonate¹⁴⁰, tin(IV) diethanolamine¹⁴¹, stannic molybdate¹¹⁵, titanium tungstate^{113,114}, stannic arsenate¹¹⁰, stannic antimonate¹⁰⁹, stannic tungstate¹⁴², stannic hexacyanoferrate(II)¹⁴³, hydrous zirconium oxide¹⁴⁴, cerium(IV) antimonate¹⁴⁵, stannic phosphate^{146,147}, zirconium phosphate⁶⁰, titanium(IV) tungstate^{148,149}, tri-*n*-butyl phosphate^{150–152}, sulfonic and carboxylic ion exchange resin¹⁵³, 2-hydroxyisobutyric acid¹⁰⁵, stannic oxide¹⁵⁴, thorium phosphate¹⁵⁵ and Al₂O₃¹⁵⁶ etc. (d) *Other surfaces* : A number of unconventional supports have been used, e.g. glass fibre paper^{135,157–159}, cellulose acetate (cellogel)^{52,160}, poly(vinyl alcohol) support¹⁶¹, cellulose acetate impregnated with 2-hydroxy-2 methylpropionic acid¹⁶² etc.

Thin layers : Various types of adsorbents have been used, e.g. silica gel^{163–166}, silica gel-G¹⁸⁶, silica gel G-starch⁹⁰, gypsum, cellulose^{83,167}, kieselguhr⁷⁹, agar⁷⁷, alumina¹⁶⁸, swelled poly vinyl alcohol¹⁶⁹ etc.

(D) Background electrolytes :

Buffer solutions : pH of buffer solution and the concentration in the layer or paper should remain constant during

operation, e.g. EDTA-ligand buffer⁵³, aqueous glycolate buffer¹¹⁹, ethylenediamine and triethylamine in potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer¹²⁰, acetylacetone at various pH¹⁷⁰, buffered EDTA^{165,171}, Michaelis buffer¹¹¹, sodium bicarbonate and sodium acetate as buffers¹⁰¹, HCl-sodium acetate¹⁷², acetate buffers¹⁰⁶, organic acid and their ammonium salts¹⁴⁰, buffer solutions⁶³, $\text{NH}_3\text{-NH}_4^+$ buffer¹⁷³, 2 : 1 mixture of aqueous buffer-propylene glycol (pH 2. 18)⁸⁰ etc. were used.

Weak electrolytes : Weakly dissociated acids, bases and salts have found widespread applications in the electrophoretic separations of metal ions and anions, e.g. ammonium hydroxide^{31,72,174}, ammonium carbonate^{67,68,73,78,175,176} etc.

Strong electrolytes : In comparison to other electrolytes, strong electrolytes¹⁵³ have been less popular due to their high conductivity.

Miscellaneous electrolytes : A large number of other electrolytes including complexing ones have been used : formic acid (Refs. 175–179); acetic acid (Refs. 24, 108, 133, 143, 177–179), lactic acid (Refs. 39, 65, 79, 95, 99, 100, 108, 123, 126, 179, 180), citric acid (Refs. 25, 37, 40, 41, 47, 48, 50, 51, 62, 108–110, 121, 129, 134, 146, 148, 149, 176, 179–182), EDTA (Refs. 42, 62, 112, 121, 129, 139, 183, 184), oxalic acid (Refs. 24, 25, 40, 110, 143, 146, 148, 149, 178, 185), tartaric acid (Refs. 25, 39, 108, 110, 121, 129, 143, 146–149, 173, 184–187), HCl (Refs. 24, 40, 46, 60, 63, 66, 70, 114, 129, 136, 142, 149–152, 156, 173, 184, 188–190), H_2SO_4 (Refs. 124, 168, 191), complexon III^{24,83}, complexing electrolytes^{192,193}. $\beta\beta'$ -diaminodiethyl ether-*N,N'*-tetra-acetic acid¹¹⁷, ethylene dinitritetetraacetic acid¹⁷¹, L-hydroxyisobutyric acid and its ammonium salt (pH = 3.2)¹³⁷, L-hydroxyisobutyric acid^{43,81,137}, aqueous and mixed H_2O -alc. media with NaNO_2 as complexing agent¹⁹⁴, 7% solution of KCNS in 66% ethanol¹⁸⁹, trichloroacetic acid^{125,195}, nitritotriacetic acid^{32,131,196}, monocarboxylic and hydroxycarboxylic acids³³, mixture of glycine and NaCl-HCl (pH = 3) and aspartic acid-NaCl³⁴, *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)iminodiacetic acid¹⁹⁵, formal-doxime¹⁹⁸, KCl^{60,66,107,156}, $\text{LiClO}_4\text{-KClO}_4$, $\text{LiClO}_4\text{-Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ¹⁵⁷, Na_2HPO_4 ¹³⁵, $\text{KNO}_3\text{-LiNO}_3$ eutectic¹⁵⁸, aqueous solution of diethylenetriamine HCl and malonic acid¹⁹⁹, cerium oxalate²⁰⁰, piperidine or hexamethylenimine¹⁸⁴, KNO_3 ¹³⁰, HClO_4 ¹⁰⁵, mixture of citric acid-NaCl⁴⁴, mixture of oxime and acetic acid⁵⁴, 2-hydroxyisobutyric acid⁵⁵, phosphoric acid or its sodium salts and their mixtures⁶⁴, lactic acid-zinc acetate (pH = 4.2)⁶⁹, nitrates of NH_4 , Mg, Cd and Al¹²², nitrates of Ca, Sr, Ba, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd, Al, Fe, La, Ce, Mg

and Th, ZrOCl_2 , MgSO_4 , $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and MgCl_2 ⁷⁰, NaOH, nitrates of NH_4 , Mg, Al and Th, ZrOCl_2 ⁶⁸, sodium barbiturate sodium acetate-sodium octanoate (pH = 8.6)¹⁰⁴, sodium carbonate¹⁶⁴, meta and polyphosphates^{201,202}, sulfates of Na, K, NH_4 , Mg and Cu²⁰³, water-methanol mixtures²⁰⁴.

(E) Detection and quantification :

For spot detection following methods are used.

Colour reactions : It involves the dipping or spraying of the paper or the spraying of the chromatoplate with suitable chromogenic and fluorogenic spary reagents forming coloured products with different species. Some of them used for the detection of cations include yellow ammonium sulfide, alizarin red-S, dithiozone, diphenylcarbazide, aluminon, alcoholic solution of dimethylglyoxime, 8-hydroxyquinoline, phosphomolybdic acid, stannous chloride in 4M HCl, quinalizarin, rhodamin-B, potassium ferrocyanide and ferricyanide chromotropic acid etc. For anions, ferric chloride, pyrogallol, silver nitrate solution in methanol, diphenylamine solution in conc. H_2SO_4 , aqueous ammonium molybdate followed by SnCl_2 and HCl, aqueous methylene blue solution, KI-HCl, sodium nitroprusside, zirconium tetrachloride and alizarin etc. are used as detectors. The detection procedures and other details are reported in literature²⁰⁵.

Fluorescence and UV detection : The spots may be detected by X-ray fluorescence¹⁷¹ or by observation with UV illumination^{120,132} by β -activity measurement²⁰⁰, by contact photographs with the aid of selective filters or by scanning procedures. This method is highly sensitive, non-destructive and amenable for spot visualization before undertaking quantitative estimation.

Radioisotope technique : The various methods used include photography^{51,100,126}, autoradiography^{37,52,64,121,126,185}, radio active tracers¹²⁷, photoelectric screening^{124–126,137,206}, radiometric detection¹⁵⁷, neutron activation, G. M. detection¹³⁶ and flame photometry^{62,132,207}.

The methods used for quantitative analysis are described below.

Visual comparison : The intensity of colour and the size of the spot varies with the quantity of the substance applied. On this basis visual comparison of spot size and colour intensities between samples and standards is used for quantification. The volume applied of standard and unknown substances should be kept equal. Visual comparison method works satisfactorily if the amounts applied are close to the detection limit.

Zone elution : It is the most accurate and widely used

method. In this, the section of paper is cut up and thin layer is scrapped off containing single species followed by elution and determination by spectrophotometry^{99,118,139,145,207,208} and other appropriate methods^{105,126}.

Spot area measurement : The method is very simple and is based upon the fact that size of the resultant spot is proportional to the concentration of the substance applied¹⁶⁸. The method works well if the spot has distinct edges.

In situ densitometry : Very small quantity of the substance can be determined with a densitometer^{194,197}. The scanning of paper strips and thin layer plates by direct densitometry is more frequently used because of its sensitivity and simplicity.

Conclusion

In the literature, suitable combinations of stabilization medium and electrolyte are available for the analysis of almost all metal ions. On the other hand, anions have been paid much less attention. In this review the references are chosen to include paper and thin layer electrophoretic methods dealing with the separation of various metal groups, different oxidation states of the same metal, rare earths, radioactive elements etc. The PE and TLE are applicable to the analysis of a variety of multicomponent mixtures except volatile or reactive substances. However, little effort is made for the analysis of geological, pharmaceutical, environmental and irradiated samples.

For the quantitative determination of inorganic species after their separation, several procedures have been developed in isolation or by coupling PE with sensitive instrumental techniques in order to widen the scope for the analysis of complex mixtures. However, environmental analysis, the need of the day, requires the development of some more sensitive techniques in this area of analytical interest to meet various hazards and for the analysis of natural and industrial microscale samples.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance. Thanks are due to Mr. Sumesh Chandra Sharma, Research Fellow, for help in preparing the manuscript.

References

1. P. K'o'nig in "A Manual of Paper Chromatography and Paper Electrophoresis", eds. R. J. Block, E. L. Durrum and G. Zweig, Academic, New York, 1958.
2. D. Von Klobusitzky and P. Konig in Ref. 1.

3. G. Berraz in Ref. 1.
4. H. J. McDonald, M. C. Urbin and M. B. Williamson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1893.
5. H. J. McDonald, M. C. Urbin and M. B. Williamson, *Science*, 1950, **112**, 227.
6. K. A. Kraus and G. W. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4329.
7. W. Grassmann and K. Hannig, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1950, **37**, 397.
8. H. Svensson and I. Brattsen in Ref. 1.
9. E. L. Durrum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2943.
10. E. L. Durrum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4875.
11. H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 356.
12. T. R. Sato, W. P. Norris and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 776.
13. H. H. Strain, T. R. Sato and W. P. Norris, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 423.
14. H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **30**, 620.
15. H. H. Strain, T. R. Sato and J. Engelke, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 90.
16. H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 818.
17. H. H. Strain and J. C. Sullivan, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 816.
18. J. L. Engelke, H. H. Strain and S. E. Wood, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1864.
19. S. E. Wood and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1869.
20. H. Sansoni and R. Klement, *Angew. Chem.*, 1953, **65**, 422.
21. H. Sansoni and R. Klement, *Angew. Chem.*, 1954, **66**, 598.
22. H. W. Wood, *Nature*, 1955, **195**, 1084.
23. H. W. Wood, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1956, 468.
24. M. K. Das, A. K. Majumdar and M. M. Chakrabarty, *Mikrochim. Ichnoanal. Acta*, 1965, **5**, 1124.
25. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, A. Ruckdeschel, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 733.
26. A. K. Majumdar and M. M. Chakrabarty, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, **17**, 228.
27. A. K. Majumdar and B. R. Singh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **18**, 224.
28. A. K. Majumdar and B. R. Singh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **18**, 220.
29. A. K. Majumdar and B. R. Singh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, **17**, 541.
30. A. K. Majumdar and B. R. Singh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **19**, 520.
31. S. Nakano, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1952, **73**, 912.
32. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, A. Ruckdeschel, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1970, **3**, 553.
33. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, A. Ruckdeschel, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1970, **6**, 1295.

34. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1971, 5, 811.
35. M. Lederer, *Research*, 1951, 4, 371.
36. M. Lederer, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1979, 171, 403.
37. M. Lederer, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1958, 1, 86.
38. R. Ito, Y. Hirata, K. Arie and K. Ohtsubo, "Proc. Symp. Solvent Extr", Osaka University, Japan, 1989, p. 95.
39. T. R. Sato, H. Diamond, W. P. Norris and H. H. Strain, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 6154.
40. H. G. Mukherjee and M. Pattanayak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 792.
41. M. Lederer, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 11, 145.
42. V. P. Shvedov and V. N. Ivanov, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1975, 49, 2716 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 13328).
43. R. Virtanen and P. Kivalo, *Suomen Kemistilehti (B)*, 1968, 41, 184 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 69, 48964).
44. Chun Chang and Po-Szu Lin, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 58, 3872.
45. R. A. G. de Carvalho, *Rev. Port. Quim.*, 1964, 6, 57 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 4924).
46. M. Lederer and J. Vernois, *Compt. Rend.*, 1957, 244, 2388 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 12716).
47. M. Lederer, *Compt. Rend.*, 1953, 236, 200 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1953, 47, 12111).
48. M. Maki, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1956, 5, 571.
49. S. Suzuki and T. Mitsuzi, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi.*, 1969, 90, 677 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 71, 85087).
50. E. K. Korchemnaya, V. I. Naumova, A. N. Ermakov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1969, 24, 1670 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 72, 62422).
51. E. K. Korchemnaya, V. I. Naumova, A. N. Ermakov and A. A. Nemodruk, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1969, 24, 1515 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 72, 18214).
52. F. Grass and R. Kittl, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1971, 2, 371.
53. V. Jokl and I. Valaskova, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1972, 72, 373.
54. M. H. Lancina, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1959, 2, 438.
55. E. Ohyoshi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1970, 43, 1387 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1971, 20, 2951).
56. G. Cetini, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, 52, 11653.
57. E. K. Korchemnaya, A. N. Ermakov and V. I. Naumova, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1970, 25, 705 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 73, 72691).
58. R. A. Bailey and L. Yaffe, *Chromatogr. Rev.*, 1961, 3, 158.
59. D. I. Ryabchikov, E. K. Korchemnaya and V. I. Naumova, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1968, 23, 741 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 69, 32646).
60. G. Alberti, A. Conte, G. Grassini and M. Lederer, *Electroanal. Chem.*, 1962, 4, 301.
61. Ying-Bo-Hai, *Acta Chim. Sinica*, 1965, 31, 263.
62. G. H. Evans and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 1560.
63. Pe-Hai-Ying and Te-Tun Cheng, *Hua Hsueh Tung Pao*, 1964, 6, 375 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 62, 2229).
64. J. L. Engelke and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1872.
65. H. Nagai and S. Kurata, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1956, 77, 451 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 15335).
66. M. Lederer, *Chem. Ind.*, 1954, 1481.
67. M. Lederer, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 606.
68. M. Lederer and M. Sinibaldi, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1971, 60, 275.
69. T. Deguchi, K. Ujimato and S. Ohashi, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1969, 18, 981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 71, 119223).
70. M. Sinibaldi and M. Lederer, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1971, 60, 241.
71. M. Lederer, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1961, 2, 174 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 55, 25600).
72. R. Consden, A. H. Gordon and A. J. P. Martin, *Biochem. J.*, 1946, 40, 33.
73. C. G. Honegger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1961, 44, 173.
74. Y. Hashimoto and I. Mori, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 6699.
75. K. Hannig and G. Pascher in "Thin Layer Chromatography – A Laboratory Hand Book", ed. E. Stahl, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1969.
76. J. R. Sargent, "Methods in Zone Electrophoresis", 2nd. ed., B. D. H. Chemicals, 1969.
77. B. Pfrunder, R. Zurfluch, H. Seiler and H. Erlenmeyer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 45, 1153 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 7951).
78. F. Dobici and G. Grassini, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1963, 10, 98.
79. A. Moghissi, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, 30, 91.
80. C. Bergamini, G. Rapi and R. Raffaelli, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 10653.
81. K. Bächmann and H. Gorisch, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1966, 23, 336.
82. W. J. Van Ooij and J. P. W. Houtman, *Fresenius. Z. Anal. Chim.*, 1968, 236, 407 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 69, 32647).
83. T. P. Makrova and A. V. Stepnov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, 26, 1823 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 76, 41522).
84. A. Vestermark and B. Wiedemann, *Nucl. Instrum. Methods*, 1967, 56, 151 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 68, 8420).
85. V. Pretorius, B. J. Hopkins and J. D. Schieke, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1974, 99, 23.
86. S. D. Sharma and S. Misra, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1991, 14, 1453.
87. S. D. Sharma and S. Misra, *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1992, 5, 141.
88. M. Pukl, M. Prosek and R. E. Kaiser, *Chromatographia*, 1994, 38, 83.
89. C. F. Poole and I. D. Wilson, *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1997, 10, 332.
90. S. D. Sharma, S. Misra and R. Agrawal, *Chem. Environ. Res.*, 1995, 4, 111.
91. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, E. Unger, A. Ruchdeschel and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1969, 5, 1070.
92. H. J. Mc Donald, J. L. Foresman and W. E. Bermes, Jr., *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1957, 94, 493.

Sharma. : Paper and thin layer electrophoresis of metal ions and anions – a review

93. P. G. Moinat and E. F. Tuller, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1655.
94. J. C. Nasi and A. Jacometti, *Rev. Bras. Farm.*, 1995, **76**, 43 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 328568).
95. J. C. Nasi and C. R. Tirapelli, *Rev. Bras. Farm.*, 1996, **77**, 173 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1997, **127**, 341107).
96. H. H. Strain and G. W. Murphy, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 50.
97. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, A. Ruckdeschel, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1970, **1**, 86.
98. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, A. Ruckdeschel, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1970, **1**, 95.
99. C. Bighi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **57**, 4020.
100. C. Bighi and G. Lucci, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **61**, 7681.
101. C. Bighi and G. Lucci, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **57**, 4020.
102. H. Meier, E. Zimmerhackl, W. Albrecht, D. Boesche, W. Hecker, P. Menge, E. Unger and G. Zeitler, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1976, **1**, 181 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 95985).
103. G. M. Varshal, I. Ya. Koshcheva, R. P. Morozova and O. N. Konopleva, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, **26**, 939 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1972, **23**, 3183).
104. B. Zmbova, V. Jovanovic and J. Bzenic, *Isotoponpraxis*, 1972, **8**, 295 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, **77**, 159732).
105. R. Virtanen and P. Kivalo, *Acta Chem. Fenn.*, 1968, **41**, 184.
106. M. Mazzei and M. Lederer, *Anal. Lett.*, 1967, **1**, 67.
107. V. V. Batashova, A. M. Babeshkin and A. N. Nesmeyanov, *Vest Mosk. Gos. Univ., Ser. Khim.*, 1970, **11**, 361 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1971, **20**, 2429).
108. R. A. Bailey and L. Yaffe, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 1871.
109. M. Qureshi, K. G. Varshney and R. P. S. Rajput, *Ann. Chim.*, 1976, **66**, 337.
110. M. Qureshi and S. D. Sharma, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, **13**, 723.
111. D. S. Shin and M. U. Han, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **6**, 29 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **59**, 60).
112. R. S. Singh, S. N. Tripathi, A. K. Ghose and A. K. Dey, *Sep. Sci.*, 1969, **4**, 171.
113. M. Qureshi, J. Kishore and R. G. Varshney, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1977, **76**, 383.
114. M. Qureshi, K. G. Varshney and F. Khan, *Sep. Sci.*, 1971, **6**, 559.
115. J. P. Rawat and P. Singh, *Ann. Chim.*, 1974, **64**, 873.
116. E. Ohara and H. Nagai, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1952, **73**, 924.
117. P. E. Wenger, W. V. Janstein and I. Kapetanidis, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1963, **1**, 97.
118. H. G. Mukherjee and A. Devi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 984.
119. R. P. Bhatnagar and F. A. K. Yusufi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 410.
120. M. S. Ghouri, Z. H. Chohan and A. Samee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 372.
121. H. Van Dijk, F. P. Ijsseling and H. Loman, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **27**, 563.
122. M. Lederer, L. Morpurgo and L. Ossicini, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, **50**, 475.
123. T. R. Sato, W. P. Norris and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 521.
124. W. E. Lingren, G. R. Reeck and R. J. Marson, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 1585.
125. M. M. Tuckerman and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 695.
126. T. R. Sato, W. E. Kisieleski, W. P. Norris and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 438.
127. T. R. Sato, W. P. Norris and H. H. Strain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 267.
128. I. N. Ermolenko and M. L. Longin, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1964, **19**, 425 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **61**, 3664).
129. A. K. Majumdar and H. G. Mukherjee, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **15**, 547.
130. J. Miller, W. F. Pickering and F. L. Ward, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **14**, 538.
131. G. Marcu and M. Tomus, *Analisis*, 1972, **1**, 43.
132. J. L. Frahn, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, **53**, 616.
133. M. Tomus and M. Totan, *Anal. Abstr.*, 1969, **17**, 2641.
134. E. K. Korchemnaya, V. I. Naumova and A. N. Ermakov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, **26**, 249, (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **74**, 119574).
135. N. G. S. Gopal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 618.
136. J. F. Facetti and M. V. de Santiago, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 1726.
137. W. Kraak and G. D. Wals, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1965, **20**, 197.
138. Pe-Hai-Yin, *Hua Hsueh Hsueh Pao*, 1965, **31**, 260 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, **63**, 15527).
139. A. K. Misra, R. P. S. Rajput, V. K. Maheshwari and D. K. Misra, *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1990, **3**, 256.
140. A. K. Misra and R. P. S. Rajput, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1990, **13**, 1435.
141. D. K. Singh, P. Mehrotra and J. Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 92.
142. M. Qureshi, K. G. Varshney, S. P. Gupta and M. P. Gupta, *Ann. Chim.*, 1976, **66**, 557.
143. K. G. Varshney, A. A. Khan and J. B. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1025.
144. A. K. Sen, S. B. Das and U. C. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 354.

- 145 R P S Rajput, A K Misra and S Agarwal, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 1988, **65**, 744
- 146 S D Sharma S Misra and T R Sharma, *Ann Chim* , 1985, **75**, 145
- 147 M Qureshi and A H Israeli, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1968, **41** 523
- 148 S D Sharma and S Misra, *J Planar Chromatogr* , 1989, **2**, 399
- 149 S D Sharma, M Gupta and R Gupta, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 2000, **77**, 307
- 150 V A Luginin and I A Tserkovnitskaya, *Chem Abstr* , 1977, **86**, 83134
- 151 V A Luginin, S Yu Kazachenko and I A Tserkovnitskaya, *Zh Anal Khim* , 1976, **31**, 2260 (*Chem Abstr* , 1977, **87**, 33150)
- 152 V A Luginin and I A Tserkovnitskaya, *Chem Abstr* 1977, **86**, 83133
- 153 T Yambe, M Seno and N Takai, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn* 1961, **34**, 738
- 154 A K Sen U C Ghosh and R K Ghatuay, *Chromatographia*, 1979, **12**, 237
- 155 A K De and K Chowdhury, *Sep Sci* , 1975, **10**, 39
- 156 M Lederer and F L Ward, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1952, **6** 355
- 157 G Alberti, S Alluli and L Palazzeschi, *J Chromatogr* , 1969, **44** 141
- 158 G Alberti, G Grassini and R Trucco *J Electroanal Chem* , 1962, **3**, 283 (*Chem Abstr* , 1962, **57**, 5280)
- 159 G Alberti, S Alluali and G Modugno, *J Chromatogr* , 1964, **15**, 420 (*Chem Abstr* , 1965, **62**, 2278)
- 160 N Mitsuo and S Masunobu, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1972, **21**, 942 (*Chem Abstr* , 1972, **77**, 121714)
- 161 J Maslowska and R Orzelowski, *Chem Anal (Warsaw)*, 1976, **21**, 219 (*Chem Abstr* , 1976, **85**, 116033)
- 162 K Aitzetmuller, K Buchtela, F Grass and F Hecht, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1966, **6** 1101
- 163 I Mori, N Tsunematsu and M Shinogi, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1969, **89**, 1669 (*Chem Abstr* , 1970, **72**, 62423)
- 164 I Mori, M Shinogi and N Tsunematsu, *Yakugaku Zasshi* 1969, **89**, 1726 (*Chem Abstr* , 1970, **72**, 62424)
- 165 R Frache and A Dadone, *Chromatographia*, 1973, **6**, 266
- 166 F Schoenhofer and F Grass, *J Radioanal Chem* , 1978, **46**, 145 (*Chem Abstr* , 1979, **90**, 33406)
- 167 E F Wagner, *Scifen-Oele-Fette-Vachse*, 1968, **94**, 27
- 168 D S Gaibakyan and S I Sagradyan, *Arm Khim Zh* . 1971, **24**, 668 (*Chem Abstr* , 1972, **76**, 10028)
- 169 J Maslowska, *Chem Anal (Warsaw)*, 1965, **10**, 1151
- 170 Z H Chohan, M S Ghouri and S Ali, *Pak J Sci Ind Res* , 1990, **33**, 474 (*Chem Abstr* , 1991, **115**, 100112)
- 171 W M Macnevin and M L Dunton, *Anal Chem* , 1957, **29** 1806
- 172 E Blasius and M Fischer, *Z Anal Chem* 1960, **177**, 28, (*Chem Abstr* , 1961, **55**, 11183)
- 173 O V Shcherbak, *Chem Abstr* , 1963, **58**, 1897
- 174 S Harasawa and A Sakamoto *J Chem Soc Jpn , Pure Chem Sect* , 1952, **73**, 614
- 175 O Schier, *Angew Chem* , 1956, **68**, 63
- 176 G DeVries, G P Schutz and E Van Dalen, *J Chromatogr* , 1964, **13**, 119
- 177 J L Frahn, *J Chromatogr* , 1979, **171**, 530
- 178 M Watanabe, T Takahara and T Yamada, *Chubu Kogyo Daigaku Kiyo*, 1967, **3**, 160 (*Chem Abstr* , 1969, **70** 16752)
- 179 T Fukuda, K Miyakawa and T Ueki, *Eiseikagaku*, 1967, **13**, 342 (*Chem Abstr* , 1968, **69**, 65807)
- 180 H H Strain, J F Binder, G H Evans, H D Frame, Jr and J J Hines, *Anal Chem* , 1961, **33**, 527
- 181 D Malysz, *Acta Polon Pharm* , 1960, **17**, 221 (*Chem Abstr* , 1961, **55**, 12773)
- 182 E K Korchemnaya, V I Naumova and B N Brmakov, *Zh Anal Khim* , 1969, **24**, 342 (*Chem Abstr* , 1969, **71**, 27111)
- 183 V A Luginin and I A Tserkovnitskaya, *Anal Abstr* 1973, **25**, 110
- 184 J Sherma, G H Evans, H D Frame, Jr and H H Strain. *Anal Chem* , 1963, **35**, 224
- 185 S Ekinci, *Turk J Nucl Sci* , 1983, **10**, 94 (*Chem Abstr* . 1984, **101**, 13665)
- 186 S K Shukla and J P Adloff, *J Chromatogr* , 1962, **8**, 501
- 187 H G Mukherjee and M Pattanayak, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 1974, **51**, 819
- 188 S K Mukherjee and M M Lahiri, *Sci Cult* , 1966, **32**, 39
- 189 M Lederer, *Nature*, 1951, **167**, 864
- 190 M Lederer and F L Ward, *Aust J Sci* , 1951, **13**, 114
- 191 W E Lingren, G R Reeck and R J Marson, *Anal Chem* , 1968, **40**, 1585
- 192 G Cetini, *Chem Abstr* , 1963, **59**, 14549
- 193 G De Angelis, P Ippoliti and A Pupella, *Chem Abstr* , 1959, **53**, 1979
- 194 R P Bhatnagar and F A K Yusuffi, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1978, **2**, 373
- 195 G Marcu and A Botar, *Anal Abstr* , 1973, **25**, 109

Sharma : Paper and thin layer electrophoresis of metal ions and anions – a review

- 196 J P Adloff and R Bertrand, *J Electroanal Chem*, 1963, **5**, 461
- 197 Z Pluklikova, V Jokl and J Majer, *Chem Zvesti*, 1969, **23**, 869 (*Chem Abstr*, 1971, **74**, 60472)
- 198 G Marcu and A Botar, *Chem Abstr*, 1969, **70** 64012
- 199 H D Frame, Jr, H H Strain and J Sherma, *Anal Chem*, 1962, **34**, 170
- 200 V P Shvedov and N A Pavlova, *Radiokhimiya*, 1959 **1**, 400
- 201 M Maki, *Jpn Analyst*, 1954, **3**, 393
- 202 M Maki, *Jpn Analyst*, 1955, **4**, 302
- 203 H C Chakraborty, *J Chromatogr*, 1961, **5**, 121
- 204 T Mitsui and Y Tsujii, *Chem Abstr*, 1974, **81**, 17508
- 205 G Zweig and J Sherma, "CRC Handbook of Chromatography", Academic, New York, 1972, Vols 1 and 2
- 206 H G Mukherjee, *Z Anal Chem*, 1961, **184**, 170
- 207 J Sherma and H H Strain, *Anal Chem*, 1962, **34**, 76
- 208 H L Joliot and M Lederer, *J Phys Radium*, 1956 **17** 497 (*Chem Abstr*, 1957, **51**, 100)